

**POLICY FRAMEWORKS, CULTURAL NORMS AND
HOUSEHOLD ENGAGEMENT IN DOMESTIC WASTE
MANAGEMENT IN KARU LOCAL GOVERNMENT,
NASARAWA STATE**

By

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Abstract

Poor domestic waste management remains a persistent challenge in many Nigerian communities, leading to environmental degradation, health hazards, and reduced quality of life. In Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State, ineffective communication of policies, weak household engagement, and culturally embedded perceptions hinder proper sanitation practices. This study examines the interplay of policy frameworks, cultural norms, and household engagement in shaping domestic waste management behaviours. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected through surveys, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews involving residents and environmental agency officials. Findings reveal that, although policies and institutional structures exist, their implementation is often weak, with limited communication to households. Cultural norms, including the perception that sanitation exercises waste time and resources, strongly influence residents' participation. Mass media channels are underutilized, reducing public awareness and compliance. Guided by Participatory Governance Theory and Cultural Theory, the study concludes that

effective and sustainable waste management requires inclusive, culturally sensitive, and well-communicated strategies that actively involve households and leverage multiple media platforms. The findings provide practical insights for policymakers, environmental agencies, and community leaders seeking to improve public engagement and environmental sanitation outcomes.

Keywords: Domestic Waste Management, Policy Frameworks, Cultural Norms, Household Engagement

Introduction

Globally, tons of municipal solid waste are generated daily, posing health and environmental threats when not properly managed (UNEP, 2013). Urban waste management has become a critical concern as cities struggle with inadequate collection and disposal systems (Rodic-Wiersma, 2013). In many developing countries, waste collection rates often fall below 70% (Rodic-Wiersma, 2013; UNEP, 2013). This is inclusive of Nigeria. Historically, waste streams were simpler mostly organic, paper, wood but modern consumption introduced plastics, chemicals, and synthetic materials, making waste management more complex and expensive (Bello, Ismail, & Kabbashi, 2016). In the African context, more than 50% of collected waste is often disposed through uncontrolled land filling (Rotich, Yongsheng, & Jun, 2006).

In Nigeria, although policies and regulations exist, implementation is weak, institutional capacity is limited, and local communities are often excluded from policy processes (Rodic-Wiersma, 2013). In Karu Local Government Area, rapid urbanization from Abuja spill over has led to high waste volumes. Despite existing waste management policies, poor infrastructure, weak local governance, and cultural norms (e.g., open dumping, burning) persist. There is a disconnect between formal policy frameworks and local cultural practices. Many households hold negative perceptions of waste as worthless material, which reduces their willingness to engage in regulated waste processes (Bello et al., 2016). Understanding how governance, culture, and household engagement interact is essential to designing more effective, locally grounded waste management strategies.

Domestic waste management has emerged as one of the most pressing environmental and public health challenges in the 21st century. Globally, the generation of municipal solid waste has reached alarming levels, with estimates ranging between 1.7 and 1.9 billion metric tons annually, and projections suggesting an increase to 2.2 billion metric tons by 2025 (UNEP, 2013). This rapid growth in waste generation has placed immense pressure on waste management systems, especially in developing countries where collection rates are typically below 70%. Poorly managed waste contributes to pollution, flooding, and outbreaks of diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and malaria (Ferronato & Torretta, 2019).

While waste management is often viewed primarily as a technical or infrastructural challenge, the literature increasingly highlights the importance of governance frameworks, cultural practices, and household participation. This review situates Karu Local Government Area (LGA) of Nasarawa State, Nigeria, within global and regional waste management debates. It focuses on three interlinked issues; policy frameworks, cultural norms, and household engagement. It is in lieu of the above that this study assessed the pre-existing government policies and traditional practices/culture of communicating and engaging households in domestic waste management in Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Global Policy Frameworks for Waste Management

Waste management at the global level is guided by multilateral agreements, international organizations, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). SDG 11 emphasizes sustainable cities and communities, while SDG 12 focuses on responsible consumption and production, with specific targets for reducing waste through prevention, reduction, recycling, and reuse. The Basel Convention regulates transboundary movements of hazardous waste, reinforcing global cooperation.

The UNEP (2013) “Guidelines for National Waste Management Strategies” highlight the need for integrated approaches combining policy, technology, and community engagement. Developed countries typically follow hierarchical waste management frameworks, prioritizing reduction, reuse, and recycling before

disposal. For example, the European Union's Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) emphasizes producer responsibility and circular economy principles. These frameworks demonstrate the central role of governance in shaping effective waste management outcomes (Rodic & Wilson, 2017).

Waste Management in Africa: Policy and Governance Gaps

In Africa, waste management is characterized by weak institutional capacity, poor enforcement, and limited infrastructure. Studies indicate that over 50% of collected waste in African cities is disposed of in uncontrolled landfills (Rotich, Yongsheng, & Jun, 2006). Cultural practices, rapid urbanization, and inadequate funding exacerbate the challenge.

Liyala (2011) emphasizes that waste management systems in East Africa are heavily centralized, often relying on imported refuse trucks. This centralization creates inefficiencies, as local governments lack resources to enforce policies or adapt systems to cultural realities. Similarly, Okot-Okumu and Nyenje (2011) argue that the disconnection between policy and local practices explains why open dumping and burning remain widespread in African households.

In addition, informal waste management such as scavenging, open burning, or household-level dumping persists despite official bans. These practices are often rooted in cultural norms and survival strategies, reflecting the limitations of purely top-down governance models (Bello, Ismail, & Kabbashi, 2016).

Nigeria's Policy Framework for Waste Management

Nigeria has developed several policies and institutions to address waste management. The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) was established under the NESREA Act (2007) to regulate environmental practices. The National Environmental Sanitation Policy (2005) provides guidelines for solid waste management, while state governments, including Nasarawa, have their own waste management laws and sanitation authorities.

Despite these frameworks, implementation remains poor. Studies show that waste collection coverage in Nigerian cities is low, and infrastructure cannot keep pace with urban growth (Agwu, 2012). A review by Ogwueleka (2009) found that

although regulations exist, enforcement is inconsistent, funding is inadequate, and communities are rarely consulted.

In Karu LGA specifically, rapid urbanization from Abuja's spill over has overwhelmed local capacity. Migrant populations have expanded settlements such as Mararaba and New Nyanya, generating large volumes of waste with minimal infrastructure to manage it (Adamu, 2014). This gap between policy and practice has allowed cultural and informal systems of waste management to persist.

Cultural Practices and Domestic Waste Management

Culture shapes how communities perceive and handle waste. In pre-colonial African societies, waste streams were largely biodegradable, consisting of leaves, food waste, and wood products. Disposal methods such as open dumping and burning were sufficient and culturally embedded (ENDA, 2006). However, modern waste streams now include plastics, nylons, and hazardous chemicals, making traditional practices inadequate and harmful (Bello et al., 2016).

In Karu, many households continue to rely on open dumping into drainages or communal heaps, and burning is common. These practices reflect a perception of waste as "worthless" and disposable without consideration of long-term environmental consequences (Saliman, 2021). Furthermore, communal sweeping still practiced in some areas demonstrates how cultural norms of shared responsibility coexist with modern challenges. The persistence of these practices suggests that policy frameworks have not effectively integrated cultural contexts. Scholars such as Posmaningsih et al. (2018) argue that cultural practices must be acknowledged and harnessed, rather than ignored, if households are to be meaningfully engaged in sustainable waste management.

Household Engagement in Waste Management

Household participation is critical to waste management success. Without active household involvement in waste separation, recycling, and disposal, even the best-designed policies will fail (Wilson, Velis, & Cheeseman, 2006). Yet, in many developing countries, households perceive waste management as solely the government's responsibility (Khulna study, Bangladesh, cited in UNEP, 2013). In Nigeria, household engagement is limited by low awareness, poverty, and inadequate infrastructure (Agwu, 2012). In Karu LGA, households often dispose

of waste indiscriminately due to lack of access to collection services or knowledge of sustainable alternatives (Adamu, 2014). The challenge is compounded by cultural attitudes that normalize poor waste practices.

Research suggests that effective household engagement requires a combination of education, incentives, and infrastructure (Simmons, Wilson, & Dean, 2021). Behaviour change communication (BCC) approaches can help shift attitudes, but these must be supported by accessible services such as regular collection, designated disposal sites, and affordable recycling options.

Gaps in Policy and Practice

The literature highlights several gaps in waste management policy and practice relevant to Karu:

1. **Policy–practice disconnect:** While policies exist at national and state levels, enforcement is weak, and local realities are rarely considered.
2. **Cultural resistance:** Traditional practices such as burning and open dumping persist, often undermining formal policies.
3. **Limited household engagement:** Households are rarely integrated into decision-making or provided with tools to participate effectively.
4. **Weak institutional capacity:** Local governments such as Karu lack the resources and infrastructure to implement existing policies.

These gaps underscore the need for a more integrated approach that bridges governance frameworks with cultural practices and household participation.

Theoretical Insights

The governance of domestic waste can be understood through participatory governance theory, which emphasizes the involvement of all stakeholders including households in decision-making. Cultural theory provides additional insights, highlighting how deeply held norms shape environmental behaviour (Douglas, 1982). Combining these perspectives suggests that waste management in Karu must be approached not just as a technical issue but as a socio-cultural and political process. Domestic waste management in Karu LGA is shaped by the intersection of policy frameworks, cultural norms, and household practices. While

national and state policies exist, weak enforcement and lack of community inclusion undermine their effectiveness. Cultural practices rooted in historical norms continue to influence household behaviours, often in ways that conflict with formal policies. Household engagement remains minimal, reflecting both structural and cultural barriers. Addressing these challenges requires policies that are culturally sensitive, community-inclusive, and backed by adequate institutional capacity. For Karu, understanding this intersection is essential to designing waste management systems that are not only technically sound but also socially sustainable.

Methodology

This quantitative and qualitative study on policy frameworks, cultural norms and household engagement in domestic waste management in Karu LGA. The study used the Yamane method to determine the number of questionnaires given to Karu LGA's 333,800 population.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

N = Total Population

E = Level of precision or error limit = 5% or 0.05

n = Sample size

Therefore

$$n = \frac{333,800}{1 + 333,800(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{333,800}{835.5}$$

$$= 399.5$$

Approximately 400

$$n = 400$$

Creating room for inaccurate filling of questionnaire and drops out (5%)

5×400

$100 = 20$

$400 + 20 = 420$

For 333,800 respondents, the researcher randomly delivered 420 questionnaires to Karu LGA residents. Triangulation was strengthened by interviews and focus groups.

Pre-existing government policies and traditional practices/culture of communicating and engaging households on domestic waste management in Karu LGA of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

s/n	Items	Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Disagree
1	The monthly sanitation exercise is practiced by all residents of Karu LGA.		80 (20.4)	196 (49.9)	117 (29.8)
2	Nasarawa State urban development board (NUDB) has been engaging residents of Karu LGA on issues of effective domestic management.		40 (10.2)	273 (69.5)	80 (20.5)
3	Nasarawa environmental protection agency (NASEPA) has made		40 (10.2)	234 (59.5)	119 (30.3)

	communication and engagement of households on managing domestic waste a priority in Karu LGA.			
4	Households in Karu LGA has enjoyed the services of waste management agency, Karu zone as they communicate and engage with residents on proper domestic waste management.	80 (20.4)	234 (59.5)	79 (20.1)
5	Radio is a medium of communicating domestic waste management to the residents of Karu LGA.	40 (10.2)	158 (40.2)	195 (49.6)
6	The national environmental sanitation policy has been broken down for better understanding for Karu LGA residents.	40 (10.2)	195 (49.6)	158 (40.2)
7	The national	40	158	195

	orientation agency (NOA) has educated us on the national policy guidelines on sanitary inspection of premises.	(10.2)	(40.2)	(49.6)
8	The national policy guidelines on solid waste management is well known and understood by residents of Karu LGA.	40 (10.2)	234 (59.5)	119 (30.3)
9	The television has been used in the communication and engagement of Karu LGA residents on issues of domestic waste management.	40 (10.2)	195 (49.6)	158 (40.2)
10	Newspapers is an effective channel for communicating and engaging Karu LGA residents on domestic waste management.	40 (10.2)	158 (40.2)	195 (49.6)

Source: Researcher’s fieldwork in Karu LGA, 2023.

The table above shows some government policies and traditional practices/culture of communicating and engaging households on domestic waste management. The first item on the table shows that 80 (20.4) respondents of the study agree that the

monthly sanitation exercise is practiced by all residents of Karu LGA. Disagreeing with the previous view, 196 (49.9) respondents strongly disagree, similarly, 117 (29.8) respondents also disagree. It can therefore be deduced from the table that the highest number of the study's respondents strongly disagree that the monthly sanitation exercise is practiced by all residents of Karu LGA. Corroborating the above view, the field and communication officer of NASEPA said that: 'The perception of people towards the monthly sanitation exercise is not encouraging at all. The people prefer to engage in their daily activities rather than take care of their environment. Having a clean environment is very important to our health and general well-being' (KII, 2023).

Substantiating the above view, a participant at the focus group discussion was of the opinion that:

Cleanliness is said to be next to godliness but this does not apply to everybody most especially people within this Karu area. We are a set of people that are mostly interested in either our jobs or businesses for us to think of engaging in the monthly sanitation exercise is a waste of time and money. In a nutshell, the number of persons that participate in the monthly sanitation is few (FGD, 2023).

Summing from the above views, it can therefore be said that, the residents of Karu local government area do not all engage in the monthly sanitation due to their perception towards sanitation, as it wastes their time and money.

The second item on the table has it that, 40 (10.2) respondents of the study agree that Nasarawa State urban development board (NUDB) has been engaging residents of Karu LGA on issues of effective domestic management. In contrast to this view, 273 (69.5) respondents strongly disagree with the claim and 80 (20.5) disagree with the claim. It can therefore be noted from the table that the highest number of the study's respondents strongly disagree that Nasarawa State urban development board (NUDB) has been engaging residents of Karu LGA on issues of effective domestic management. Corroborating the above view, the field and communication officer of NASEPA said that 'Nasarawa urban and development board, handles issues that has to do with land and building of structures within the

states. It guides residents to follow the laid down blueprint so as not to have structures built in an unorganised way' (KII, 2023).

Agreeing with the above view, a participant during the FGD session said that, "I only see the function of NUDB whenever a person is raising a structure, they will write on the structure using a red marker for the person to seek for permission from them before proceeding with his/her work". The function of NUDB does not involve sanitation issues per say but building of structures within the approved areas of the state.

The third item has it that 40 (10.2) respondents of the study agree that Nasarawa environmental protection agency (NASEPA) has made communication and engagement of households on managing domestic waste a priority in Karu LGA. In contrast to the above view, 234 (59.5) respondents strongly disagree to the above claim, similarly, 119 (30.3) respondents also disagreed with the above claim. It can therefore be inferred from the table that the highest number of the study's respondents strongly disagree that Nasarawa environmental protection agency (NASEPA) has made communication and engagement of households on managing domestic waste a priority in Karu LGA. Agreeing with the above position, an FGD participant said that, "Nasarawa environmental protection agency has not made management of domestic household a priority. If management of domestic household waste is made a priority and we are taught, there would be less waste to be seen around" (FGD, 2023). In contrast with the above submission, the field and communication officer of NASEPA said that, "NASEPA is known for anything that has to do with environment; basically sanitation and we have made everything about sanitation a priority" (KII, 2023).

The fourth item on the table shows that, 80 (20.4) respondents of the study agree that households in Karu LGA has enjoyed the services of waste management agency, Karu zone as they communicate and engage residents on proper domestic waste management. In a different view, 234 (59.5) and 79 (20.1) respondents strongly disagree and disagree with the above claim. It can therefore be deduced from the table that the highest number of the study's respondents strongly disagree that households in Karu LGA have enjoyed the services of waste management agency, Karu zone as they communicate and engage residents on proper domestic waste management. Agreeing with the above position, a

participant at the FGD session said that, “Karu zone waste management agency does not communicate and engage residents on proper domestic waste management but rather they only carry waste from sites around the communities to the approved waste dumping sites” (FGD, 2023). In a different purview, the field and communication officer of NASEPA said that “they are different from waste management Karu zone, so he cannot say anything about them. It can therefore be said that waste management Karu zone does what is done at NASEPA.

The fifth item on the tables has it that, 40 (10.2) respondents strongly agree that radio is a medium of communicating domestic waste management to the residents of Karu LGA. Giving a different purview, 158 (40.2) and 195 (49.6) strongly disagree and disagree respectively to the above claim. It can therefore be deduced from the table that the highest number of the study’s respondents disagree that radio is a medium of communicating domestic waste management to the residents of Karu LGA. Agreeing with the above view point, a participant said that, “radio is not used in the communication of domestic waste management rather it is used for announcement making, reminding people of the day of sanitation” (FGD, 2023). The field and communication officer of NASEPA said that, “we don’t frequent the radio house to discuss issues of domestic waste but announcements are normally made for people to clean their houses and surroundings on the last Saturday of every month” (KII, 2023). The implication of the above is that people are not well informed on the management of domestic waste but rather they are told to clean their houses on the last Saturday of every month. Radio is a good channel that should be used but it is not used or not effectively used which is the reason for the dirt we see in Karu LGA.

The sixth item has it that 40 (10.2) respondents agree that the national environmental sanitation policy has been broken down for better understand for Karu LGA residents. In a different light, 195 (49.6) and 158 (40.2) respondents of the study strongly disagree and disagree to the above claim. It can therefore be noted from the table above that the highest number of the study’s respondents strongly disagree that the national environmental sanitation policy has been broken down for better understand for Karu LGA residents. Furthering the argument, a participant at the FGD session said that, “we are good at policy

making, but breaking it down for understanding of all and sundry and executing the policy is a serious problem with the Nigerian society as a whole” (FGD, 2023). The field and communication officer of NASEPA said that: ‘We don’t handle issues of policy rather we execute policies and anything that has to do with national policy, is not done by us. But we have at different times broken down policies of the national environmental sanitation policy through our activities in the state’ (KII, 2023).

The implication that this presents for this study, is that people may not effectively understand policies that has to do with environment due to the fact that they may be not be available for them or they may not be lettered enough to read the policies. Once an issue of this nature is prevalent, the understanding and corporation or execution of such a policy becomes an issue.

The seventh item on the table shows that 40 (10.2) respondents of the study agree that the national orientation agency (NOA) has educated them on the national policy guidelines on sanitary inspection of premises. Providing a different purview to the above 158 (40.2) and 195 (49.6) strongly disagree and disagree to the above claim. It can therefore be deduced from the table that the highest number of the study’s respondents disagree that the national orientation agency (NOA) has educated them on the national policy guidelines on sanitary inspection of premises. Agreeing with the above, view point, a participant at the FGD, session said that “the National Orientation Agency mostly educates people on issues that are emergencies and there are priorities to these issues, it may be possible that domestic waste management issues are not yet a priority” (FGD, 2023). The field and communication officer said that “we have not interfaced with NOA but we hope to interface with them if the required resources are made available for us” (KII, 2023).

The eighth item on the table shows that 40 (10.2) respondents of the study agree that the national policy guidelines on solid waste management is well known and understood by residents of Karu LGA. In contrast to the above view point, 234 (59.5) and 119 (30.3) respondents strongly disagree and disagree to the above claim. It can therefore be noted from the table that the highest number of the study’s respondents strongly disagree that the national policy guidelines on solid waste management is well known and understood by residents of Karu LGA. The

field and communication officer agreeing with the above view said that “the residents have not understood the national policy on solid waste management because of the attitude which the people of Karu LGA exhibit; this may be as a result of their perception or lack of domestic waste management knowledge” (KII, 2023). In another vein, a participant at the FGD session said that:

The national policy guidelines on solid waste management can be known and understood by residents only when they are taught or exposed to the guidelines. We may be exposed to the policies if some people do research on their own. To the best of my knowledge, I have not come across any sensitization regarding policies on solid waste management (FGD, 2023).

Summing the above view, the national policy guidelines on solid waste management is not well known and understood by residents of Karu LGA and this affects their knowledge, attitude and practice of domestic waste management.

The ninth item on the table shows that 40 (10.2) respondents of the study agree that television has been used in the communication and engagement with Karu LGA residents on issues of domestic waste management. In a different light, 195 (49.6) and 158 (40.2) respondents strongly disagree and disagree to the above claim. It can therefore be deduced from the above table that the highest number of the study’s respondents strongly disagree that television has been used in the communication and engagement with Karu LGA residents on issues of domestic waste management. The field and communication officer of NASEPA agreed with the above view when he said that:

We rarely use television in communicating issues of domestic waste management, what you may see at times is the state owned Television station that may capture our activities in the state and report at their station. We can be interviewed in the process of doing our work or at the television station, but the interviewing at the television station is a once in a while session (KII, 2023).

Giving another view to the above point, an FGD participant is of the view that:

Television is not used in the communication of domestic waste management, may be the agency that is responsible for educating the people on issues of domestic waste management should interact with the television

stations within the state to show domestic waste management documentary, this may help people to understand the importance and how to effectively manage domestic waste (FGD, 2023).

The position of the FGD participant shows alternative way in which television can be used to communicate on domestic waste management in the state and by extension the nation. The tenth item on the above table has it that 40 (10.2) respondents of the study agree that newspapers is an effective channel for communicating and engaging Karu LGA residents on domestic waste management. In contrast to the above, 158 (40.2) and 195 (49.6) respondents of the study strongly disagree and disagree with the above view point. Inferring from the table it can be deduced that the highest number of the study's respondents disagree that newspapers is an effective channel for communicating and engaging Karu LGA residents on domestic waste management. Substantiating the above position, a participant at the FGD session said that: 'Newspapers have not been used in the communication of domestic waste management. It can be because of the capital involved but one important area to note is that the number of people that patronage newspapers is little in comparison with other channels of communication' (FGD, 2023). Corroborating the above point, the field and communication officer of NASEPA said that "newspapers are used in the communication of domestic waste management to residents of the state" (KII, 2023).

Discussion of Findings

This study examined government policies, institutional practices, and communication strategies in domestic waste management in Karu Local Government Area (LGA) through the lenses of Participatory Governance Theory and Cultural Theory. The findings reveal that ineffective citizen participation, weak institutional engagement, and culturally embedded perceptions significantly undermine domestic waste management efforts. These outcomes both support and extend existing literature on environmental sanitation in Nigeria.

From the perspective of Participatory Governance Theory, effective governance requires active collaboration between government institutions and citizens in decision-making, implementation, and evaluation of public policies. However,

findings from this study indicate minimal resident involvement in environmental sanitation activities, particularly the monthly sanitation exercise. The majority of respondents strongly disagreed that all residents participate, a position corroborated by KII and FGD data. This reflects a breakdown in participatory mechanisms, where residents are treated as passive recipients of directives rather than active stakeholders. Similar conclusions were reached by Okeke, Mohammed, and Garba (2024), who argue that weak citizen engagement in waste management programmes leads to poor ownership and low compliance.

Furthermore, the poor engagement of residents by agencies such as NASEPA and the Waste Management Agency, Karu Zone, contradicts the principles of participatory governance, which emphasize dialogue, inclusion, and shared responsibility. Although NASEPA officials claim that sanitation is a priority, residents' contrary perceptions suggest that participation is largely symbolic rather than substantive. This aligns with Ezeaka and Bartholomew (2025), who contend that environmental governance in Nigeria often lacks meaningful grassroots involvement, thereby limiting behavioural change.

Cultural Theory provides additional insight into residents' attitudes and behaviours toward sanitation. The findings show that many residents perceive monthly sanitation exercises as a waste of time and money, prioritizing economic activities over environmental cleanliness. These perceptions reflect culturally embedded values that emphasize immediate economic survival over collective environmental responsibility. Cultural Theory explains that such shared beliefs and social norms shape how communities interpret and respond to government policies. This finding supports Awashima and Santas' (2025) observation that without culturally sensitive communication, sanitation programmes are often resisted or ignored.

The study also revealed significant confusion regarding institutional roles, particularly concerning the Nasarawa State Urban Development Board (NUDB). Most respondents disagreed that NUDB engages in domestic waste management, a view supported by both KII and FGD data. From a participatory governance standpoint, unclear institutional mandates weaken accountability and public trust. Cultural Theory further suggests that when institutions are perceived as distant or irrelevant to everyday life, communities disengage from their initiatives. This

reinforces Okeke et al.'s (2024) argument that poor inter-agency coordination undermines effective environmental governance.

Another critical finding is the underutilization of mass media channels such as radio, television, and newspapers in communicating domestic waste management practices. Participatory Governance Theory emphasizes information sharing as a prerequisite for citizen participation; however, the findings show that media are mainly used for sanitation reminders rather than education. This supports Awashima and Santas (2025), who found that limited media engagement restricts public understanding and participation. From a cultural perspective, failure to use familiar and trusted media platforms limits the ability to reshape norms and values related to waste management.

The findings on policy awareness further underscore theoretical implications. Most respondents disagreed that national environmental sanitation policies and solid waste management guidelines have been broken down for public understanding. Participatory governance requires policies to be accessible and co-created with citizens; however, this study shows that policies remain largely top-down. Cultural Theory explains that abstract policy documents, when not translated into local languages or contexts, fail to resonate with community values, thereby reducing compliance. This supports findings from studies in Jos and Karu LGA, which link low environmental literacy to poor waste management practices.

Additionally, the limited involvement of the National Orientation Agency (NOA) in sanitation education highlights weak institutional collaboration. Participatory Governance Theory suggests that effective governance thrives on multi-stakeholder partnerships, yet the absence of coordinated action between NOA and environmental agencies restricts widespread sensitization. Culturally, this limits repeated exposure to sanitation messages necessary to normalize positive waste management behaviours within communities.

The findings demonstrate that domestic waste management challenges in Karu LGA stem from both structural governance failures and cultural perceptions. The absence of participatory platforms, weak communication strategies, and culturally insensitive approaches has resulted in poor public engagement and limited policy

awareness. Consistent with existing literature, this study affirms that sustainable domestic waste management requires not only functional institutions but also inclusive governance structures and culturally grounded communication strategies. Integrating participatory governance mechanisms with culturally informed sensitization programmes is therefore essential for improving domestic waste management practices in Karu LGA.

Conclusion

Policy frameworks, cultural norms, and household engagement in domestic waste management in Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State was the thesis of this study. The findings reveal that, although policies and institutional structures exist, their implementation and communication to households are largely ineffective. Residents demonstrated low participation in monthly sanitation exercises, limited understanding of national environmental sanitation and solid waste management policies, and minimal engagement with agencies responsible for waste management.

Cultural norms emerged as a significant factor influencing residents' behaviour, with many perceiving sanitation activities as a waste of time and resources. These findings, interpreted through Cultural Theory, highlight how shared beliefs, social values, and community practices shape attitudes toward environmental sanitation. From the perspective of Participatory Governance Theory, the study highlights a gap between government intentions and citizen participation, showing that the absence of inclusive engagement mechanisms undermines policy effectiveness and compliance.

The study also found that communication channels, including radio, television, and newspapers, are underutilized for educating residents on domestic waste management, while existing sensitization efforts are often limited to reminders for sanitation exercises. This weakens the ability of households to internalize policy guidelines and adopt sustainable waste management practices.

Conclusively, sustainable domestic waste management in Karu LGA is constrained by institutional, cultural, and communication challenges. The study demonstrates that achieving effective household engagement requires integrated strategies; clear policy communication, culturally sensitive interventions, active

participation of residents in decision-making, and improved use of media and outreach channels. Addressing these gaps is critical for fostering public awareness, behavioural change, and compliance, ultimately leading to a cleaner, healthier, and more sustainable environment.

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